

Polarographic Study of Cd^{2+} with Schiff Base, bis-*p*-methoxy benzyliminoethane in DMF—Water media

T. B. TRIVEDI, M. S. PATEL and D. N. VYAS

University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar.

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The complexation of Cd^{2+} with the Schiff base bis-*p*-methoxy benzylimino ethane, has been investigated polarographically in dimethyl formamide water mixtures. The metal to ligand ratio of the complex is found 1 : 1 in the mixed solvent used. Stability constants are calculated at three different temperatures and thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the complexation have been reported. A relationship between pH and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of the system is shown by empirical equation similar to the polarographic wave equation. Ligand proton stability constant is evaluated by utilizing this equation and verified potentiometrically. The effect of solvent on complex composition is discussed.

THE complexation behaviour of the Schiff bases have been investigated by several workers¹⁻⁴. The work reported so far in the literature is not much. A little attention is paid to the evaluation of thermodynamic functions of Schiff base complexes using polarographic technique.

The present work deals with the polarographic study of Cd-bis-*p*-methoxy benzyliminoethane complex in 40% DMF-water medium as a part of our programme to study the nature of Schiff base complexes of transition and nontransition metals. The effects of pH , temperature and composition of mixed solvent are studied in order to throw some light on the stability of the complex. The temperature effect is utilized in evaluating thermodynamic functions and the pH effect in determination of the protonation constant of the ligand which is the novel aspect of the present work. The protonation constant is verified potentiometrically utilizing Irving & Rossotti half integer method⁵.

Experimental :

All the chemicals used were of 'AnalaR' (BDH) grade. The ligand was prepared by standard method⁶ using anisaldehyde and ethylene diamine in 2 : 1 mole ratio. The product was purified and recrystallized from benzene, m.p. 109°.

Polarograms were recorded manually on Toshniwal Polarograph CLO2A with Beltronix microammeter after bubbling oxygenfree nitrogen through the system for 20 minutes. Inert atmosphere was maintained over the system during measurements. Temperature was controlled within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ using Toshniwal thermostat GL 15. The capillary had

the characteristics $cm^2/s^{\frac{1}{2}}/i^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2.05 \text{ mg.}^{\frac{2}{3}} \text{ sec}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ in 0.8 M KNO_3 at 1.0 V. vs. S.C.E.

The effect of pH was studied using the solution containing 0.1 mM Cd^{2+} , 0.0103M Ligand, 0.8M KNO_3 and 0.005% gelatin. Different pH values were adjusted using either 0.1M. NaOH or 0.1 M HNO_3 .

Other polarographic measurements were carried out at the optimum $pH 7.6 \pm 0.05$, (considering solubility of the ligand and the stability of the complex). The ionic strength μ was kept constant with 0.8 M KNO_3 .

As the ligand is insoluble in water, DMF-water mixtures were used as solvent considering suitability of DMF in nonaqueous polarography⁷. In the present work, 40% DMF-water mixture was found to be the most appropriate. The halfwave potentials were obtained from the plots of $\log i/i_{\frac{1}{2}} - i$ vs. E d.m.e.

Potentiometric method was also applied to determine the metal ligand ratio and the ligand proton stability constant in 40% DMF-water medium at 30°. Three sets were prepared.

- i. 0.01 M HNO_3 + 0.10 M KNO_3
- ii. 0.01 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M Ligand + 0.10 M KNO_3
- iii. 0.01 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M Ligand + 0.002 M Cd^{2+} + 0.10M KNO_3

Total volume in each set was adjusted to 50 ml. All the sets were titrated against 1.0 M CO_2 free NaOH.

Theory :

The number of ligands per Cd²⁺ was estimated by using the expression⁸ :

$$p = \frac{d(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c}{d \log C_x} \left[\frac{2.303RT}{nF} \right] \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where C_x = ligand concentration

-(E_{1/2})_c = half wave potential of the complex

p was calculated from the slope of the graph -(E_{1/2})_c vs. log C_x. The stability constant of the complex was determined using Lingane's relation⁹ :

$$(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c = (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln K - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln C_x^p \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Results and Discussion :

The reduction of the complex at d.m.e. gives a well-defined wave which is found to be diffusion controlled and reversible as revealed from the plot of i_a vs. √^hcorr and slopes (28 ± 2 mV) of log i/i_a-i vs. E_a d.m.e. The slope value obtained is somewhat less than expected as generally found for aqueous non-aqueous mixed systems¹⁰.

(1) *Effect of ligand concentration :* -

The cathodic shift in E_{1/2} on increasing ligand concentration shows the formation of the complex (Table-1). The plot of (E_{1/2})_c vs. log C_x is a straight

TABLE-1

Polarographic characteristics of Cd²⁺ with Schiff base in 40% DMF

Sr. No.	Ligand x 10 ³ M	Con.	Temp. °C	E _{1/2} V. (vs SCE)	i _{pd} A
1.	0.00	30	0.589	2.10	
		40	0.584	2.75	
		50	0.579	3.25	
2.	5.17	30	0.631	1.80	
		40	0.620	2.13	
		50	0.614	2.50	
3.	10.30	30	0.643	1.75	
		40	0.635	2.05	
		50	0.629	2.40	
4.	15.50	30	0.650	1.63	
		40	0.643	2.05	
		50	0.636	2.33	
5.	20.70	30	0.655	1.50	
		40	0.648	1.83	
		50	0.642	2.12	
6.	25.90	30	0.658	1.38	
		40	0.652	1.65	
		50	0.647	1.88	
7.	31.00	30	0.665	1.35	
		40	0.661	1.60	
		50	0.655	1.80	

line at all the temperatures. The value of p calculated from its slope is unity, hence only 1 : 1 complex

is formed. Though the co-ordination number of Cd (which is 4) and the structure of the ligand (a bi-dentate one) suggest a strong possibility of the formation of 1 : 2 complex ; 1 : 1 complex is observed in 40% DMF-water medium repeatedly. DMF itself is a complexing solvent and hence solvation can take place to such an extent that it can even compete with the ligand. Such observations are reported in the literature¹¹. Further, to verify this fact the complete study is repeated¹² in 50% ethanol water medium—a less complexing medium and the value obtained for p is 1.8. The graph of E_{1/2} vs. log C_x is a straight line showing possibility of 1 : 2 complex only. The potentiometric study of Cd²⁺ with this ligand¹² in 40% DMF gives the formation curve extending upto n̄=1, which suggests the possibility of 1 : 1 complex.

(2) *Effect of temperature :*

The system has been studied at three different temperatures and an increase in temperature causes an increase in diffusion co-efficient giving rise to increase in diffusion current at the rate < 1.8%/°C. The anodic shift in E_{1/2} and decrease in stability constant value with the rise in temperature indicate the ease of reduction and less stability of the complex respectively at the higher temperature.

The change in free energy (ΔG), heat content (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been calculated

TABLE-2

Temp. °C.	Log K	ΔH k. cal/mole	ΔG k. cal/mole	ΔS cal°c/mole
30	3.84	-5.584	-5.325	-0.855
40	3.71	-5.584	-5.314	-0.863
50	3.59	-5.584	-5.307	-0.867

(table-2) using equations¹³ :

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

$$\frac{d \log K}{d (1/T)} = \Delta H / 2.303 R \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

$$\Delta S = (\Delta H - \Delta G) / T \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

The plot of log K vs 1/T is a straight line, from the slope of which ΔH is determined. The free energy change (ΔG) is greater at lower temperature than that at higher one and the entropy change is less negative at lower temperature than at the higher one. Both these observations suggest that the complexation is more favoured at lower temperatures¹⁴.

(3) *Effect of pH :*

The dependence of (E_{1/2})_c on the pH of the solution (0.1 mM Cd²⁺, 0.0103 M ligand, 0.8 M KNO₃)

is represented by the graph $(E_{1/2})_a$ vs pH in Fig. 1. $(E_{1/2})_o$ is independent of pH except the region between pH 6.0 and 10.5, where it acutely depends on pH . It may be due to the fact that below pH 6.0 ligand is completely protonated while above pH 10.5 it is totally free from protonation. Between these limits ligand can have varying extent of protonation and more stability of the complex at higher pH might be due to this effect (observed from more negative shift of $E_{1/2}$ with pH). The following relation is suggested for the graph of $-(E_{1/2})_o$ vs. pH (Fig.1)

Probable Chemical Changes :

The more complexation at higher pH is based on the nature of the ligand and can be explained as follows :

The probable structure of the ligand is ---

where R is.....

Fig 1 The graph of $-(E_{1/2})_c$ (vs. SCE) vs. pH Cd^{2+} 0.1mM, Ligand $1.03 \times 10^{-2}M$

$$pH = (pH_{1/2}) + A \log \frac{(E_{1/2})_c}{(E_{1/2})_{of} - (E_{1/2})_o} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

where $(E_{1/2})_o = E_{1/2}^{\cdot}$ of the complex

$(E_{1/2})_{of} =$ limiting value of $(E_{1/2})_o$

The above equation is similar to the polarographic reversible wave equation and the $(pH)_{1/2}$ is the pH at the inflection point of the wave. The plot of $\log(E_{1/2})_{of}/(E_{1/2})_{of} - (E_{1/2})_o$ vs. pH is a straight line (Fig. 2) indicating validity of equation (6).

At pH below 6.0

Free ligand

Totally protonated ligand.

At $pH = (pH)_{1/2}$

Dissociation of the protonated ligand can be

represented as follows :

At $\text{pH}=(\text{pH})_{\frac{1}{2}}$ the dissociation of ligand can be given by :

The above chemical changes can be generalized as :

where L represents the ligand and n is the number of protons.

The overall dissociation constant of the protonated ligand can be given as :

$$K_d = \frac{[\text{L}][\text{H}^+]^n}{[\text{LH}_n^{n+}]}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{hence } -\log K_d &= -\log \frac{[\text{L}]}{[\text{LH}_n^{n+}]} - n \log [\text{H}^+] \\
 &= -\log \frac{[\text{L}]}{[\text{LH}_n^{n+}]} + n \text{pH} \dots \dots (11)
 \end{aligned}$$

at $(\text{pH})_{\frac{1}{2}}$ the protonation has proceeded upto exactly one half, hence $[\text{L}] = [\text{LH}_n^{n+}]$ and $-\log K_d = n \cdot (\text{pH})_{\frac{1}{2}} \dots \dots \dots (12)$

Equation (12) renders it possible to calculate the dissociation constant of the protonated ligand provided the value of n is known.

In fig. 1 value of $(\text{pH})_{\frac{1}{2}}$ is 8.5 and the structure of the ligand suggests that n=2 and accordingly dissociation constant K_d comes out to be 10^{-17} .

If one wants to calculate the stepwise proton dissociation constant then equation (10) should be simply written as :

$$\text{and } -\log K_d = \log \frac{[\text{LH}_n^{n+}]}{[\text{LH}_{n-1}^{(n-1)+}]} + \text{pH} \dots \dots \dots (14)$$

In the present case for the dissociation of the first proton from the protonated ligand LH_2^{2+} , in the equation 14).

$[LH_2^{2+}] = [LH^+]$ at $(pH)_{\frac{3}{2}}$ as seen from equation (8), hence $-\log K_{a1} = (pH)_{\frac{3}{2}}$ and from fig. 1 $(pH)_{\frac{3}{2}} = 8.0$

Therefore first dissociation constant $K_{a1} = 10^{-8}$. Similarly at $(pH)_{\frac{5}{2}}$ the equilibrium is as per equation (9) and in the equation—

$$-\log K_{a2} = \log \frac{[LH^+]}{[L]} + pH \dots\dots\dots (15)$$

$[LH^+] = [L]$, at $(pH)_{\frac{5}{2}}$ as seen from eqn. (q) from fig. 1 $(pH)_{\frac{5}{2}} = 9.0$ and accordingly second dissociation constant $K_{a2} = 10^{-9}$.

The dissociation constants of the protonated ligand were also calculated applying Irving and Rossotti half integer method⁵ to the potentiometric results. The results are in agreement with the conclusions drawn from polarographic observations. The value of K_a , K'_{a1} and K'_{a2} are $10^{-17.0}$; $10^{-7.5}$ and $10^{-9.5}$ respectively.

The importance of polarographic method for evaluation of ligand protonation constant lies in the fact, that the constant can be obtained even when the ligand is not available in the free form, which is not possible with the potentiometric method. For any complex species which give the curve of the type shown in fig. 1, proton ligand stability constant can be determined by above method. Thus, it may be of use in determining proton dissociation constant for any naturally occurring complex whose ligand can not be obtained in the free form.

(4) Effect of DMF concentration :

Effect of DMF concentration is shown in Table-3. The half wave potential shifts to more negative values with decrease in diffusion current as the per cent amount of DMF increases, indicating more complexation, and less ease of reduction.

TABLE-3

Effect of solvencomposition on i_d & $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of complex. Ligand conc. 0.0517M; KNO_3 conc: 0.8 M; $Cd^{2+} = 0.1$ mM; temp. 30.4°C.

% of DMF (V/V)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ V. (vs. SCE)	i_d μA
10	0.614	2.775
20	0.616	2.650
30	0.622	2.375
40	0.630	1.930
50	0.640	1.825

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